

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

IR64 compared with recently released ASD16 and other IR varieties

S. R. S. Ranganasamy. C. A. Palanisamy, K. Natarajamoorthy. S. Palanisami, R. Velusamy, and S. M. Lal, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore, India

IR64 was compared with recently released TNAU variety ASD16 and IR50, IR60, and IR62 in a Summer 1986 trial. The random block replicated trial

Table 2. Resistance^a of ASD16 and 4 IR varieties to pests and diseases at Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	Reaction to insects				Reaction to diseases	
	BPH	GLH	WBPH	BB	B1	RTV
IR50	S	S	S	S	S	MR
IR60	S	MR	S	S	R	R
IR62	R	R	R	R	RR	
IR64	R	R	R	R	RR	
ASD16	S	S	S	MR	MR	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 1. Performance of ASD16 and 4 IR varieties at Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	Empty grains/panicle	Grain yield (g/plant)	Straw yield (g/plant)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
IR50	110	69.5	10	111	23	12.4	9.1	21.2	4.6
IR60	115	72.8	11	108	20	11.7	8.9	21.3	4.8
IR62	125	82.1	9	110	20	15.3	13.6	23.9	4.6
IR64	120	83.1	11	118	16	18.2	12.9	26.9	5.0
ASD16	115	97.2	8	102	19	16.7	15.4	24.2	4.8
CD		3.5	2.2	9.5	—	3.4	—	1.5	—

was planted 3 Apr and harvested on 6 Oct. At harvest, 10 plants from each replication were assessed for yield and yield-contributing characters.

IR64 yielded 5.0 t/ha, 0.2 t/ha more than ASD16 and IR60 (Table 1). IR64 and IR62 compare in height, but IR62 takes 5 d longer to mature. The grain of

IR64 is long slender.

IR64 is resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), green leafhopper (GLH), and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and moderately resistant to blast (B1), bacterial blight (BB), and tungro (RTV) (Table 2). □

A simplified method to classify rice varieties with isozymes

J. C. Glaszmann, Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrières, Centre International de Recherche Agronomique pour le Développement, and Plant Breeding Department, IRR

Analyses of isozyme variation at 15 to 21 loci among traditional *O. sativa* rices from all continents have led to the identification of 6 varietal groups: indica (group I); japonica, with its temperate

and tropical forms (group VI), and 4 marginal groups restricted to the north of the Indian subcontinent (groups II to V). The method used to determine the classification of a given variety involves at least 15 loci and requires electrophoretic survey of at least 10 enzymes.

We have developed a simplified procedure based on five diagnostic genes which permit classifying most varieties. These genes are *Pgi-1* and *Pgi-2*, which encode phosphoglucose isomerases, and *Amp-3*, *Amp-2*, and *Amp-1*, which